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LARGE SCALE MIMO-INTERVAL SYSTEM REDUCTION USING IMPROVED SRAM

G. V. K. R. SASTRY AND VIJAYA KUMAR D.

Abstract

This paper presents a new procedure as an improvement to a very recent method, Simplified Routh Approximation Method (SRAM), for the order reduction of high order MIMO interval systems. The proposed method (ISRAM) also preserves the impulse energy of the original system in its reduced order models besides retaining its stability to achieve improved impulse response approximation.

Keywords: Large scale system modeling, Interval system reduction, Discrete systems